

ISic4368

Dedication to Hercules Nouritanus by Caius Fannius and the Frentrani

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Carmine Ampolo

Contributors

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

Found in excavation in March 2008 in secondary deposition, having been re-used in antiquity on the street bordering the north-east side of the so-called 'insula romana' villa on Capo Boeo

Coordinates

37.804838, 12.430456

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 24-26 cm

Width 150 cm

Depth 94 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-3: 50 mm

Line 4: 30-35 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: Not measured mm

Text

1. C (aius) Fannius Min (ati) f (ilius) ceivesq [ue] Frentran [eiq]uei in Sicilia Sicelia
2. colunt Hercolei Nouritano fanum faciundum
3. coiraverunt. Pecunia conlata est n (ummi) HS (sestertii) DCXLIIS
4. [---]RAC[]V[]QV []DEDE [---]

Apparatus

Text of Ampolo 2016, compared against photograph

Translation (en)

Gaius Fannius, son of Minatus, and the citizens of the Frentrani who dwell in Sicily saw to the

construction of the temple of Hercules Nouritanus. The money collected was 643 and a half sestertii.

[-----]

Translation (it)

Gaio Fannio, figlio di Minato, e i cittadini Frentrani che abitano in Sicilia fecero fare il tempio

ad Ercole Nuritano. E stato raccolto il denaro, sesterzi seicentoquarantatre(mila?) e mezzo

Commentary

Gaius Fannius cannot be immediately identified, but is perhaps to be connected to the family associated subsequently with Sextus Pompeius. Hercules Nuritanus is not otherwise attested. Ampolo suggests the name implies a connection with Sardinia.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

1888-. *L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2016.0622

Ampolo, C. 2016. Il culto di Ercole a Lilibeo: un nuovo documento dei rapporti tra genti e culture diverse nella Sicilia occidentale. *Mare Internum. Archeologia e culture del Mediterraneo*. 8: 21-37.

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